

MULTISCALE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF 3D BRAIDED COMPOSITE STRUCTURE BY COUPLING FEM AND FFT METHOD

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Keywords: Multiscale analysis, Fast Fourier Transforms, Braided composites, Computation efficiency.

ABSTRACT

The progressive damage behavior of three dimensional (3D) braided composite beam is studied by using a more efficient multiscale coupling method including fast Fourier transformation (FFT)-based method and finite element (FE) method. FFT-based method with variational principle is used to overcome the poor convergence for composites with large jumps of material properties in mesoscale. The mechanical response of the braided composites is studied using finite element (FE) method in the macro-scale. The predicted strength and dominated failure modes of the braided composites structure obtained by the proposed method are in good agreement with the experimental results. The high computation efficiency is attractive for large structure with the nonlinear mechanical behavior.

1 INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional (3D) braided composites have been widely used in solid rocket, airplane and sports equipment, etc. However, it is difficult to adequately analyze the nonlinear mechanical behavior of the relatively larger 3D braided composite structures with complex internal geometries characteristics. Multiscale modeling is an arising tool to study the behavior of large complex structure by coupling macroscale and microscale to deeply understand the internal damage mechanisms of the structure in the different scales.

Recently, FE-based sequential multiscale method was used to analyze the mechanical properties of 3D braided composites [1-3], in which the effective properties is transferred from lower scale to higher scale. However, this sequential multiscale method cannot present the two-way transmission of information between different scales. Balokas [4] studied the effect of uncertainties on the elastic properties of 3D braided composites by using a novel neural multiscale method. Feyel [5] and Özdemir et al. [6] developed finite element method (FE2), which is a concurrent multiscale method, to model the behavior of highly heterogeneous structures. It should be noted that in FE2 method every integration point in the macroscopic scale is replaced with a RVC. Generally, these multiscale methods can be recognized as a valid way to solve the mechanical response of 3D braided composite structures. However, these numerical multiscale methods based on finite element method (FEM) should assemble element stiffness matrix in both scales, which can result in the high computational costs. An alternative efficient method based on fast Fourier transformation (FFT) was introduced to solve an equivalent micro periodic BVP by Moulinec et al. [7, 8]. The calculation of FFT-based method is carried out on a regular pixel grid (2D) or voxel grid (3D), which avoids meshing geometry and assembling stiffness matrix. Thus, in our previous work [9], the nonlinear FFT-based method combining with variational principle [10,11] is developed to simulate the damage and failure of 3D four directional braided composites in the mesoscale. However, this model neglects the influence of macroscopic boundary conditions and the relationship between macro structure failure and internal material damage, which could not reflect the damage mechanisms of macro structure subjected to external loads.

In the present study, the nonlinear mechanical behaviors of 3D four-step braided composite beam structure under bending load is studied using a more versatile and efficient numerical multiscale method similar to FE2 method, where the nonlinear FFT-based method combining with variational

principle is used to study the mechanical properties of RVC in the mesoscale. Ultimate load-bearing ability and complex failure behavior of the braided composites beam structure can be obtained by the proposed multiscale approach.

2. MULTISCALE COUPLING METHOD

The 3D four directional composite exhibits a hierarchical structure with multiple length-scales. Macroscale means the whole structure or the sample, while the mesoscale is corresponding a RVC. The coupling technique for FEM and FFT in each iteration computation are introduced as follows.

2.1 FFT-based approach using in the mesoscale

When a RVC Ω_0 with periodic boundary conditions is subjected to a strain loading, the local strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(x)$ can be split into homogenous average strain \mathbf{E} and a fluctuation strain tensor $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*(x)$, the equilibrium equation can be expressed as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(x) = \mathbf{K}(d(x)) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*(x) + \mathbf{E}) = \mathbf{K}(d(x)) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(x), \quad x \in \Omega_0, \quad (1a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*(x) + \mathbf{E}) = 0, \quad (1b)$$

where, $d(x)$ is damage state variable for each voxel grid within the RVE, and $\mathbf{K}(d(x))$ is local tangent stiffness tensor with damage variable, which can be determined by damage initiation and development criteria. As for 3D braided composites, it can be characterized by damage initiation criterion and stiffness degradation model.

The damage initiation criteria of braid yarns can be expressed as

$$I_L = \max\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{11}^{yt}}, \frac{-\sigma_{11}}{F_{11}^{yc}}\right), \quad (2)$$

$$I_T = \max\left(\frac{\max(\sigma_2, \sigma_3)}{F_{22}^{yt}}, \frac{-\min(\sigma_2, \sigma_3)}{F_{22}^{yc}}\right), \quad (3)$$

$$I_S = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}}{F_{12}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_i (i=2,3)$ and $\sigma_{ij} (i,j=1,2,3)$ are principle stresses and stress components for braid yarns, F_{11}^{yt} , F_{11}^{yc} , F_{22}^{yt} , F_{22}^{yc} and F_{12} are the longitudinal tensile strength, longitudinal compressive strength, transverse tensile strength, transverse compressive strength and shear strength of braid yarn, respectively.

The damage initiation criterion of matrix adopted the von Mises yield criterion. The elastic moduli of inner braid yarn and matrix can be updated by utilizing stiffness degradation method, which can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{y11} &= 0.001E_{y11}^0 & I_L > 1 \\ E_{y11} &= E_{y11}^0 & I_L \leq 1 \\ E_{y22} &= E_{y33} = \max(0.001, \min(D_T, D_S))E_{y22}^0, \\ G_{y12} &= G_{y13} = \max(0.001, \min(D_T, D_S))G_{y22}^0 \\ E_m &= \max(0.001, D_T)E_m^0 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where the superscript 0 denotes the undamaged state values of braid yarn or matrix. Then, the $\mathbf{K}(d(x))$ in Eq. (1a) can be obtained at each step.

Combining with variational principle, the implicit nonlinear equilibrium Eq. (1) can be rewritten by the following linear equation in Fourier space, which is described in details in the literature [11].

$$\mathcal{F}^{-1} \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{G}} : \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{K}(d(x)) : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \right\} = -\mathcal{F}^{-1} \left\{ \hat{\mathbf{G}} : \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{K}(d(x)) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

where, \mathcal{F}^{-1} and \mathcal{F} denote the discrete inverse FFT and FFT, respectively. $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i$ and $\delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are the strain and the strain increment, respectively. This linearized system can be solved using the conjugate gradient (CG) method based on the generalized minimal residual method (GMRES) to obtain the mechanical

behaviors of the RVE. The unknown stress tensor and strain tensor can be updated by the following incremental iteration form:

$$\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{i+1} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i + \delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ \delta\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}_i(d(x)) : \delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{i+1} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_i + \delta\boldsymbol{\sigma} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The initial strain load \mathbf{E} of each step applied to the above FFT-based method can be obtained from the macroscale at a certain integration point. It should be noted that the strain tensor of each integration point is calculated on the macroscale by FEM, which is not necessary to be accurately known in advance, only the entire multiscale coupling iterative process is required to identify the strain load conditions of the RVC corresponding to each integration points under each iteration step.

2.2 Coupling treatment between mesoscale and macroscale

The computation models for 3D braided composites include mesoscopic and macroscopic models. The RVC of the braided composites considering the interior braid configurations is discretized by voxels and solved by FFT-based method. A braided composites structure recognizing as homogenous material is discretized with finite element meshes and solved iteratively with Newton-Raphson method. One integration point of finite element in the macroscale is corresponding to a RVC in the mesoscale. The information between two scales relates each integration point and RVC. The macroscopic strain of each integration point in the macroscale can be transferred to RVC of 3D braided composites as boundary conditions. The macroscopic stiffness matrix, stress and damage states of each macroscopic integration point are modified using the mesoscale RVC information. The deformation information between macroscale and mesoscale cannot be coupled directly in the proposed multiscale method.

The macroscopic stress can be obtained using volume averaging over the whole domain V of the RVC under macroscopic strain loading, can be expressed as

$$\Sigma = \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle = \frac{1}{|V|} \int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} dv, \quad (8)$$

where $\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle$ is the macroscopic stress, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the mesoscopic stress of RVC.

The macroscopic tangential stiffness matrix \mathbf{C} may be degraded due to the existed damage in the RVC. Thus, the tangential stiffness matrix should be updated for finite element method in the macroscale. Based on the damage state for each point in the RVC, the macroscopic tangential stiffness matrix for finite element model can be evaluated. Six small perturbation strains $\delta\mathbf{E}$ are applied upon the mesoscale RVC. The stress responses for each point in the mesoscale RVC can be obtained by using FFT method. After one small perturbation strain is applied on RVC, the averaging stress for each component calculated by Eq. (8) can be used to calculate the one column of macroscopic tangential stiffness matrix \mathbf{C} .

To display the damage state in the macroscale, the damage variable for each integration point of the finite element should be calculated by using the damage states of RVC, and can be expressed as

$$D_i = \frac{C_{ii}}{C_{ii}^0} \quad (i=1, \dots, 6), \quad (9)$$

where C_{ii}^0 is initial stiffness component corresponding to integration point of finite element.

The mesoscale calculation is activated when the integration point of macro element belongs to the dangerous area judged by von Mises criteria.

3. COMPUTATION MODEL AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The nonlinear mechanical properties of 3D braided composite beam under bending load as shown in Fig. 1 are studied by the multiscale coupling method as mentioned in section 2. The length, width and thickness of the 3D braided composite beam are 90mm, 20mm and 6mm, respectively. The span length between two support points is 78.4 mm. The geometry sizes of RVC for the 3D braided

composites are 3.59mm×2.23mm×2.33mm. The mesoscopic braid configurations do not take into account. Thus, three finite elements in the thickness direction of the 3D braided composite beam are adopted. The element edge lengths for the macroscale finite elements are approximately close to the geometry sizes of RVC. The macroscopic finite element model of the 3D braided composites beam has 882 isoparametric finite elements as shown in Fig. 1. The meso RVC generated by TexGen corresponding to each integration point is discretized by 150000 voxels as seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of current multiscale approach.

Material	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	G_{23} (GPa)	ν_{12}
Carbon fiber	230	40	24	14.3	0.25
Epoxy resin	3.5				0.35

Table 1: Mechanical properties of fiber and resin.

In the present study, the 3D braided composites are recognized as four directional braided composites, in which the braid yarns are distributed in the four directions. The reinforced fiber and matrix are 12K T300 carbon fiber and TDE-85 epoxy resin, respectively. The fiber volume fraction V_f and inner braided angle γ are 54% and 42°, respectively. The mechanical properties of carbon fiber and resin are listed in Table 1. Additionally, the strength parameters of yarn and resin are given in Table 2.

Yarn	F_1^{YT}	F_1^{YC}	F_2^{YT}	F_2^{YC}	S_L	S_T
	1168Mpa	740Mpa	99Mpa	99Mpa	68.6Mpa	450Mpa
Resin	F_T^M			F_C^M		
	99Mpa			99Mpa		

Table 2: Strength properties of braid yarn and matrix.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Effective elastic properties

In the multiscale coupling method, the real-time stiffness of the RVC corresponding to each macroscopic integration point should be updated if the damage is appeared in the meso RVC. Thus, it is necessary to guarantee the accuracy of the prediction of RVC model by using FFT method. The comparisons of elastic constant E1 of 3D braided composites between predicted results and literatures

[12, 13] is provided in Fig. 2. It can be found that the result of RVC obtained by FFT-based method is close to experimental results in Refs. [12, 13]. The simulated result lower than experimental result can be attributed to that RVC just denotes the inner structure, while the experimental specimen is a whole structure including inner, corner and surface braid structures. The error of current predicted result is 6.6% compared with the experimental result, which is reasonable and acceptable.

Fig. 2. Comparisons between measured and predicted elastic constant E_1 of 3D braided composites.

4.2. Failure analysis

Using the present multiscale coupling method, load-displacement curve of the 3D braided composite beam under three-point bending load is provided in Fig. 3. It can be found that the load-displacement curve obtained by present multiscale method is close to that of experiment [14]. Before the damage initiation, the simulated result is lower than the experimental result. The middle section of the curve is slightly higher with the increase of loading, which may be attributed to the ideal numerical model without considering yarn distortion and internal defects. Once the damage occurs, the curve is gradually lower than the experimental result owing to the large stiffness reduction.

Figure 3: Bending load-displacement curves of 3D braided composites beam.

In addition, the bending strength can be defined as the following formulation relating to critical bending load, expressed as

$$\sigma_i = \frac{3Pl}{2bh^2}, \quad (10)$$

where, P denotes the ultimate bending load, l represents the effective span of the beam, which is 78.4mm according to the Ref. [14], b and h are width and thickness of the beam, respectively.

The damage mechanisms of the 3D braided composite beam under bending load are further studied. Fig. 4 shows the macroscopic damage development states corresponding to three points (I, II, III) selected from the load-displacement curve. It can be found that the damage and failure is initiated at compression zone, subsequent to the tension zone, and further extended to the intermediate region in the thickness direction. The fracture location and morphology obtained by the present multiscale method is consistent with experimental fracture morphologies as shown in Fig. 5 [15].

Figure 4: Macroscopic damage propagation of 3D braided composites beam under bending load.

Figure 5: Fracture morphologies of 3D four directional braided composite after bending testing [15], (a) compression side, and (b) tension side.

The mesoscopic RVC damage results corresponding to one integration point in the damage region are shown in Fig.6 to further study inner damage mechanisms, in which only the interior dominant damage modes are shown. It should be noted that the numbers in the top of legend indicate damage modes (1-Longitudinal damage; 2-Transverse damage), load step, macro-element label and integration point label, respectively. It can be found that the matrix and braid yarns at the upper surface of the 3D braided composite beam occur longitudinal compression damage and failure at first, which will lead to a great reduction in stiffness at compression surface. The deformed neutral face of the beam will be offset to the tension side, which results in the decrease of stress level of the tension side. Thus, the damage in the tension side of the beam is delayed. In the tension side of beam, the RVE mainly exhibits the matrix damage and braid yarn transverse damage. Thus, the macroscopic beam structure does not fail immediately in Fig. 4, which is consistent with the experimental observations [14].

It should be emphasized that the computation efficiency of the present multiscale coupling method is greatly higher than other directly multiscale numerical method such as FE2. As for the progressive damage of the present beam model with 7056 integration points, it can be estimated that FE2 will require about 24054 ($7056 \times (150000 / 220000 \times 5)$) days without parallel computing, which is unacceptable and infeasible, while the present multiscale coupling method just takes 10 days on the computer of Inter(R) Core(TM) i5-4590 CPU @3.30Ghz without parallel computing. Thus, the coupled FE-FFT method can be effectively applied to accurately study the failure analysis of complex structures in engineering computation.

Figure 6: Interior mesoscopic RVC damage propagation of 3D braided composite beam under bending load.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The multiscale coupling method is combining the FE and FFT method, which is used to study the mechanical behaviors of 3D braided composites beam with large braiding angle under bending load. The damage mechanisms in the macroscopic and mesoscopic scales can be well simulated. The macroscopic structure damage is connected with interior mesoscale structure damage. When the 3D braided composite beam is subjected to the bending load, the initial damage of the beam occurs in the upper side of the beam due to the compression damage and failure of the inner yarns and the matrix. With increasing macroscopic load, the damage occurs in the lower side of beam due to the transverse damage of interior braid yarns and matrix damage, where matrix damage plays a dominant role. These damage and failure process of the braided composites beam are in good agreement with the experimental phenomenon. The fully coupled FE-FFT multiscale method can be recognized as an efficient tool to study the progressive damage analysis of 3D braided composites structures under complex external boundary conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant Nos. 11672089 and 11732002), the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (Grant No. HIT.NSRIF.2017017) and Natural Science Foundation of Heilongjiang Province, China (Grant No. A2017003).

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